

The effect of Gaia-based data on grid-search models for 16 Cyg A+B and α Cen

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Abstract: Modelling astroseismically known stars by searching for best-fitting models in stellar grids naturally depends on the number and precision of known stellar parameters, limiting the range of acceptable models. Here, we compare the solutions of such grid-based analyses of the seismic benchmark object 16 Cyg A+B as obtained using the approach of Nsamba et al. (2021), with an updated search including a Gaia-based luminosity (Yildiz et al. 2017). We repeat the exercise for α Cen A, the object with unknown core structure (radiative or convective; Nsamba et al. 2018), using either a parallax-based luminosity (Kervella et al. 2017) or the stellar radius as obtained from (interferometry; Kervella et al. 2003) to restrict the space of possible solutions.

Our model grid:

We adopted a grid of stellar models following Nsamba et al. (2021) and extended it for a mass range of $[0.7 - 1.6] M_{\odot}$. The stellar grid was constructed using the 1D stellar evolution code MESA (version 9793; Paxton et al. 2015, 2018). The grid parameters in mass and composition are:

$M \in [0.7 - 1.6] M_{\odot}$ in steps of $0.05 M_{\odot}$;

$Z \in [0.004 - 0.04]$ in steps of 0.002;

Initial helium mass fraction $Y \in [0.22 - 0.32]$ in steps of 0.02;

mixing length parameter $\in [1.2 - 3.0]$ in steps of 0.2.

The stellar models were always evolved from the zero-age main sequence (ZAMS) to the end of the main sequence phase, i.e. the terminal-age main sequence (TAMS).

For each of the models their corresponding adiabatic oscillation frequencies for the spherical mode degrees, $l = 0, 1, 2,$ and 3 were calculated using GYRE (Townsend & Teitler 2013). Surface corrections by Ball & Gizon (2014) were applied.

Best-fitting models were identified by using the MCMC+Bayes tool AIMS (Rendle et al. 2019), using individual oscillation frequencies, plus T_{eff} and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ as the classical global stellar quantities.

In a second set of models also Gaia-based luminosities were added.

In order to ensure in the optimization process an essential contribution from all our sets of observable constraints, we define χ^2 in the usual way, weighing the seismic terms however by the number of “classical” over “seismic” constraints. The total χ^2 is used to obtain the likelihood function, from which the posterior probability distributions (PDF) for the different stellar properties and their uncertainties are calculated in form of the statistical mean and standard deviation, respectively.

Observable constraints

Parameter	16Cyg A	16 Cyg B	Alpha Centauri A
Effective temperature (K)	5825 ± 50	5750 ± 50	5832 ± 62
Metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ (dex)	0.1 ± 0.03	0.05 ± 0.02	0.23 ± 0.05
Luminosity (Solar L)	1.56 ± 0.05	1.27 ± 0.04	1.521 ± 0.015
Interferometric radius (Solar R)	1.22 ± 0.02 (white et al. 2013)	1.12 ± 0.02 (white et al. 2013)	1.231 ± 0.0036 (Kervella et al. 2003)

Procedure:

We repeated the grid-searches for both 16 Cyg components as in Nsamba et al. (2021), using the observables as mentioned before. These are given to the left of the resulting probability distributions for mass and radius (red entries and lines). We then repeated the grid-search by adding the Gaia-based luminosity (Yildiz et al. 2017) to the “classical” or “atmospheric” constraints. The results are shown in blue. On the right of the histograms we also give the mass resp. radius of the corresponding best-fitting model. In case of the radius we also list the interferometric radius for comparison. For α Cen A, the dynamical mass of the star is also included (left figure in case III).

I. 16 Cyg A

Result:

The additional “Gaia-luminosity” does not change the parameters of the best-fitting model, but leads to a higher probability for it, and a narrower distribution of acceptable models.

The radius of the best-fitting model remains at the upper edge of the interferometric range.

II. 16 Cyg B

Result:

The influence of the additional “Gaia-luminosity” in the grid-based modelling is very similar to that for 16 Cyg A. Mass and radius of the best-fitting model hardly change, but become more likely, the number of acceptable models is reduced.

The radius of the best-fitting model agrees very well with the interferometric measurement.

III. α Cen A

Result:

In this case, the additional luminosity constraint is reducing the model distribution on the high-mass end, but strengthens the bimodal (convective or radiative core) solution range. The underlying degeneracy between mass and helium (Nsamba et al. 2021) is not broken.

Using the interferometric radius instead of the luminosity as additional constraint (green line), drastically reduces the acceptable model distribution, leads to a mass in excellent agreement with the dynamical mass of α Cen A, and thus prefers a convective core.

Conclusion: For the well-known benchmark objects 16 Cyg A and B the additional luminosity constraint has the main effect of reducing the uncertainty in the range of acceptable models. For α Cen A it does not resolve the open question about the core structure, convective or radiative because of the mass-helium-degeneracy. However, an accurate radius measurement has a drastic effect as it breaks this due to the influence of helium abundance on opacities and therefore radius. The best-fitting models have a reasonable initial helium abundance of $Y_i = 0.282 \pm 0.012$, while the broader distributions include also models with sub-BBN helium contents.

References: Ball & Gizon, A&A 568, A123 (2014); Kervella et al., A&A 404, 1087 (2003); Kervella et al. A&A 597, A137 (2017); Nsamba et al., MNRAS 479, 55 (2018); Nsamba et al., MNRAS 500, 54 (2021); Paxton et al., ApJS 220, 15 (2015); Paxton et al., ApJS 234, 34 (2018); Rendle et al., MNRAS 484, 771 (2019); Townsend & Teitler, MNRAS 435, 3406 (2013); White et al., MNRAS 433, 1262 (2013); Yildiz et al., MNRAS 470, L25 - L28 (2017).